

NOAO Accelerates the Universe

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The NOAO celebration of 25 years of dark energy takes me right back in time to a night in early 1994 in the control room of the Mayall 4-meter Telescope on Kitt Peak, observing deep, wide fields in the I band with Marc Postman and Tod Lauer. We were combining our observing nights since my team’s deep supernova search program (the Supernova Cosmology Project), and Marc and Tod’s Deep, Wide Galaxy Survey (with Bill Oegerle and John Hoessel) both needed as much deep, wide data as we could get. Observing with Marc and Tod was a new experience: they were past masters at the game and by this point had their patten tuned as they kept themselves amused through the long night of careful work by issuing what I took as Star Trek-style commands to each other (*is that right, Tod?*) as they monitored and adjusted the observations in what they called the Deeprange Project.

For my team, the Supernova Cosmology Project, the stakes were also high, because we had invested a large collection of hard-won telescope nights at multiple telescopes around the world, all scheduled (after much time-trading and cajoling of telescope schedulers) around a new approach to systematizing high-redshift supernova discovery-and-follow-up. In our previous stage of the project, we had managed to

demonstrate the ability to discover at least one supernova at very high redshift ($z = 0.48$), but the follow-up of such a faint object was extremely difficult to obtain through the response to an IAU telegram and calls to observers at the larger telescopes; such a follow-up observation was a much bigger ask than the usual, much brighter, nearby supernova. But now with this coordinated telescope campaign, we were going to show that it was possible to find a whole “batch” of such high-redshift supernova on demand, not just one, and this time discover them all on the rising part of their lightcurves, and all just before New Moon, so that *pre-scheduled* spectroscopy could identify the Type Ia supernova and obtain their redshifts.

We had learned our lesson from the previous observing work, most of which had been clouded out, so this time we were doing the search with double the observing time ostensibly required, scheduling two telescopes back-to-back to observe the same fields from the entirely separate sites on Earth in case either one was clouded (the Isaac Newton Telescope on La Palma was the other site). We also developed a new observing strategy where we would compare observations taken just before New Moon to observations taken just after

Figure 1: The project’s state of play **before NOAO telescopes joined**: one high-redshift SN Ia discovered at a random time. (Saul’s transparencies from 1992; Credit: Perlmutter et al.1997)

Figure 2: **The KPNO Mayall 4-meter Telescope** joins the project, using the new “batch” search strategy: a half-a-dozen high-redshift SNe Ia discovered at a pre-scheduled date, just before New Moon, and all before their maximum light. (Slides from Saul’s Aguablava presentation to SN community, June 1995; Credit: Perlmutter et al. 1995)

the previous New Moon, thus guaranteeing that a Type Ia supernova discovered in the second observation but not present in the first would not have had time to reach its peak before the following dark time. If we could find and study a few dozen supernovae at redshifts of order $z \sim 0.4$, we could measure the expected deceleration of the universe’s expansion with sufficient accuracy to determine if we live in an open or closed universe, and whether the Universe would last forever or end in a big crunch.

The plan worked, and starting in March of 1994 we were able to send out IAU telegrams with a batch of half-a-dozen newly discovered Type Ia supernovae, all with extensive follow-up observations over their lightcurves. (I’m pretty sure that Marc and Tod had a good Deeperange run, too.) From then on, we could apply for telescope time with a clear demonstration of a successful approach to systematic studies of distant supernovae – and we turned our attention to the new Big Throughput Camera that Gary Bernstein was building with Tony Tyson for NOAO’s Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope.

This NOAO facility was the perfect match to our program: the wider-field camera guaranteed more supernova discoveries from each observing run, and the extremely stable, clear Chilean summer weather meant that we had much higher odds of a successful search, so our extensive follow-up campaign at many telescopes wouldn’t be wasted. In practice,

starting in 1995 we could discover and follow about 10 or more distant supernovae each semester; and other NOAO telescopes and observers in Chile and Kitt Peak were active in these follow-up campaigns. I still am grateful to the great efforts of all the NOAO schedulers and queue-observers to make it possible to systematically catch these live supernovae in action. And NOAO’s WIYN queue observing, a novelty at the time, made this work much more efficient. (Thank you Di Harmer, Paul Smith, and Daryl Willmarth, the WIYN queue observers!)

The discoveries were becoming so predictable that we were able to add the *Hubble Space Telescope (HST)* to the suite of scheduled follow-up. We realized that we could tell them well in advance which square degrees on the sky would have supernovae discoveries in them, so that the *HST* observing schedule could be laid down in advance, and then we would tweak the coordinates just the week before the observation once we had actually made the discoveries.

Now that we were observing at CTIO with this standardized approach, we began having company in the high-redshift-supernova game. Brian Schmidt, working with NOAO’s Nick Suntzeff, began developing a competing team (the High-Z Supernova Team), also using CTIO for searching, building on an experienced group of supernova experts, including members of the earlier Calan/Tololo Supernova Survey. The Calan/Tololo survey was a highly successful low-redshift

Observing Proposal Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory

Date: March 31, 1995

Proposal number:

TITLE: Homogeneity and Rate of High-Redshift Supernovae with Three Other Wide-Field Imaging Projects for Cosmology:

Gravitational Lens Search, >1-Degree Galaxy Correlation Study, and Very High-Redshift QSO Survey.

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Abstract of Scientific Justification: We propose to discover and study a sample of >12 Type Ia supernovae at redshifts $0.3 < z < 0.6$, in R-band observations of a 6.9 square degree area. This data will also be used for a search for gravitational weak lensing, a >1-degree galaxy-angular-correlation study, and a very high-redshift QSO survey by the co-investigators and collaborators. By observing this area twice, with approximately three weeks separation, we will find Type Ia supernovae on the rising side of the lightcurve and thus be able to follow up with *scheduled* photometry and spectroscopy. (We base these rates on our previous discovery and follow-up study of 7 supernovae at redshifts between 0.3 and 0.5 in a coordinated search at the INT and the KPNO 4m telescopes using the same search strategy and analysis techniques.) This study will address the homogeneity and rate of high-redshift Type Ia supernovae, with the goal of using supernovae to measure q_0 .

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SUPERNOVAE
 The Supernova Cosmology Project [S. Perlmutter, S. Deustos, G. Goldhaber, D. Groom, I. Hook, A. Kim, H. Kim, J. Lee, J. Melbourne, C. Pennyacker, and I. Small, Lawrence Berkeley Lab. and the Center for Particle Astrophysics; A. Goobar, Univ. of Stockholm; R. Pain, CNRS, Paris; E. Ellis and R. McMahon, Inst. of Astronomy, Cambridge; and B. Boyle, P. Nugent, D. Carter, and M. Irwin, Royal Greenwich Obs.; with A. V. Filippenko and A. Barth (Univ. of California, Berkeley) at the Keck telescope; W. Couch (Univ. of N.S.W.) and M. Dopita and J. Gould (Mt. Stromlo and Siding Spring Obs.) at the Siding Spring 2.3-m telescope; H. Newberg (Fermi National Accelerator Lab.) and D. York (Univ. of Chicago) at the AEC telescope] report eleven supernovae found with the CfDT1 70cm (CTIO) 4-m telescope in their 1995 High-Redshift Supernovae Search:

SN	1995 UT	R.A. (2000)	Decl.	R	Offset
1995aq	Nov. 19	0 29 04.26	+ 7 51 20.0	22.4	0".6 W, 1".4 S
1995ar	Nov. 19	1 01 20.41	+ 4 18 33.8	23.1	2".9 W, 0".5 S
1995as	Nov. 19	1 01 35.30	+ 4 26 14.8	23.3	0".7 W, 0".7 N
1995at	Nov. 20	1 04 50.94	+ 4 33 53.0	22.7	0".3 W, 0".4 S
1995au	Oct. 29	1 18 32.60	+ 7 54 03.5	20.7	1".4 E, 3".3 N
1995av	Nov. 20	2 01 36.75	+ 3 18 55.2	20.1	0".2 W, 0".0 N
1995aw	Nov. 19	2 24 55.54	+ 0 53 07.5	22.5	0".2 W, 0".2 S
1995ax	Nov. 19	2 26 25.80	+ 0 48 44.2	22.6	0".3 W, 0".2 S
1995ay	Nov. 20	3 01 07.52	+ 0 22 19.4	22.7	0".9 W, 1".4 S
1995az	Nov. 20	4 40 33.59	- 5 30 03.6	24.0	1".6 W, 1".7 N
1995ba	Nov. 20	8 19 06.46	+ 7 43 21.2	22.6	0".1 E, 0".2 N

The spectra (Hook, Nov. 26-28) are consistent with type-I supernovae (except SN 1995ar, a probable type II) at the redshift of the host galaxy: $z = 0.45, 0.46, 0.49$ (preliminary type-I identification), 0.65, 0.16, 0.30, 0.4 (supernovae redshift only), 0.61, 0.48, 0.45, 0.39. The previous observations not showing the supernovae (to limiting mag about 24) were on Oct. 29-30 at the CTIO 4-m (except SN 1995au, on 1994 Sept. 29 at the Kitt Peak 4-m telescope). Contact saul@LBL.gov for finding charts.

1995 December 6 (6270) Daniel W. E. Green

Figure 3: **The CTIO Blanco joins** the project, using the new "batch" search strategy: 11 high-redshift SNe Ia discovered at a pre-scheduled date, just before New Moon, and all before their maximum light. Shown are the CTIO proposal and the resulting IAU telegram.

supernova project (and another collaboration with NOAO people and facilities) that provided some of the best-observed low-redshift Type Ia supernovae, making it possible to calibrate the supernovae for the distance measurements at high redshift — the later results all depended on this. (Our Supernova Cosmology Project team and the new High-Z team

were now often scheduled one right after the other at CTIO, and we would pass each other coming and going in the La Serena offices on our way to and from the mountaintop.)

Two years later, our Supernova Cosmology Project team was analyzing 42 Type Ia supernovae (an auspicious number for

Figure 4: **The Blanco searches become routine:** Our set of well-observed high-redshift SNe Ia becomes big enough to measure the deceleration/acceleration of the universe, and HST follow-up can also be scheduled. (Saul's transparencies from 1997)

Cosmology from Type Ia Supernovae

Figure 5: The results: 42 SNe analyzed – almost all discovered at NOAO telescopes – showing a Universe dominated by dark energy. (Supernova Cosmology Project poster from January 1998 AAS meeting and newspaper report the next morning)

fans of another sci fi series), with data anchored by our NOAO discoveries and follow-up but now also with our extensive Keck spectroscopy and even some *HST* photometry. The measurement of deceleration turned out to be a discovery of current acceleration – both competing teams agreed! – and we are now celebrating the 25-year anniversary of what Mike Turner dubbed Dark Energy.

NOAO telescopes, both old and new, have remained in the game ever since, with further supernova work – over 2,000 SNe Ia are in our most recent compilation study! – and with other measurement approaches triangulating in on this mystery; notably the weak lensing measurements with the Dark Energy Survey (DES) project at the Blanco, and the baryon acoustic oscillation (BAO) measurements with the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) project at the Mayall. Two other long-planned efforts to address dark energy are now coming to fruition, with NOIRLab’s Vera C. Rubin Observatory’s Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) and NASA’s Nancy Grace Roman Telescope.

Well before the 50-year anniversary of dark energy, we hope to have accomplished our next major step in understanding this acceleration of the Universe’s expansion and the putative dark energy that powers it. Meanwhile, congratulations to all

the NOAO staff for more than a quarter century of unparalleled work, carrying us into the discovery and study of dark energy!

References

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